

× × × ×

MEDICINE AND NATURAL ONLINE CONFERENCE

INDEX:
GOOGLE SCHOLAR
ZENODO (DOI)
RESEARCHGATES

Information:
<https://urlc.net/M-42>

Medicine and natural online conference

ADOLESCENCE PERIOD AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF WORKING WITH TEENAGERS

Darvishkhojaye Hasan Abdulhakimovich

University of Business and Science

Teacher of Pedagogy and psychological branch

Abstract. *Unique details of the adolescence period and psychological effects of working with adults having stressed are covered in this article. Useful suggestions are given to work with teenagers having depression.*

Keywords. *Stages of personal development, adolescence, transition period in a child, period of myself and depression.*

Adolescence period is the most different than other periods of human beings with being full of its changeable movements. Due to this unique statement, make strict decisions, rushing and having a tendency to be alone are usually occurred in movements of adults.

Beginning of realized types of “myself” period and its factors is experienced in this period. This is continued with most difficult questions about realizing themselves in the mentality of both girls and boys and reasons, dreams about finding answer for these questions in this life. In most cases, these factors are used for personality in order to identify “who he or she is” or “why these signs are important” and “for whom they are important”. [1]

G.Grim claimed that adolescence period is seen between 13 and 16 ages for boys and from 12 to 15 ages for girls in mentality development of person, D.B Elkonin was divide this period in two stages in development of mentality in mankind:

a) The period of adolescence is small - under the age of 15 to the age of 10 years; the main activity - personal internal communication,

b) Older teens or early teens in the social age - 16 years of age up to 17 years of age; the main activity - reading-the professional choice.

Educational psychologist V.A. Krutesky while creation of ontogenetic man's mission in development phase, he found the content of the period of the age under the age of 11 to the age of 15 years will be defined as period of teens.

Based on D.I.Feldshteyn other researchers in contrast, the period of adolescence is divided into three stages. According to his agenda, the first stage (10-11 years) including to discover relationship to himself, the person with the decision to come to feel and are finished to himself as strictly. The second stage at the age of 12-13 teenagers include, on the one hand, to recognize himself as a person, on the other hand, has the feature of being in a negative relationship to himself. The third stage consists of 14-15 years age older adults older and, if in quick self-evaluation tend to shall be in connection with the description. [1]

In the adolescence period, sometimes the child becoming inside of some emotions, such as anger, crustiness, the emotions of the parents to take care of the excess resistance is not stable display, inhibitions and self and loved ones`

Medicine and natural online conference

requirements that may put more opportunity than to the concerns of the audience throws.

Therefore, the teenagers of the world movement need to be understood the causes of origin. For this case parents, psychologists and teachers must realize that children face with difficult age period.

The reason why this is called transition period, teenager considers himself as a member of the family, begins to realize as equal members of society. In social relationships meant not only himself, but his future progress is formed upcoming plans. Of course, these plans still perfect, is not exactly, but teens have a very big conscience. The teens living in their wished world are tend to protect their dreams from other older aged people with their all affords they had.

This is really important how the older people behave themselves in such kind of situations, but even experienced people want to say their words to teens without considering difficulties of this period.

As a result, balance the relationship between adults and young people from each other will be lost and they will go away. The level of teens knowledge about law and values of society and compatibility of their personal ideology impact entering position of society and older aged community.

Of course, at this age, teenagers still are not great, but do not want to be a child, even for this reason, it is important to care adults in many ways for independent life. It is necessary for their parents.

Some parents wish their children from the troubles of real life environment protection in order not exceeding, and excessive caring they will show, but parents ought to consider that teaching of labor in the family is a foundation of formation of a sense of responsibility, self-respect and duty of citizenship.

Relationship with only their peers, in some cases, may be reason for decrease of teens educational performance. Idea of their peers about them becomes really important.

Also, the past of mental disorders observed in this period that would be gained or impact to genetics that need to be considered.

With the emergence of depression in children symptoms, immediately need to aiding to get out of the situation. To do this, we offer the following practical recommendations:

- 1) Chat with the children, his condition with interest, about the futur, plans doing together, creating supports to herself and the formation of the required confidence to the future.

A child was never judged for their "frowned upon", "foolish" situations, instead, his excellent personal qualities need to show to be worthwhile. The child should not never be compared with their smart and lucky peers.

These comparisons also decrease extra sense of honor. Instead, comparing with past condition to the current one will be able to create far more positive changes.

- 2) Working with the individual child, completing different sessions together with children , they should feel your kindness. It is recommended to change the same daily life little.

Medicine and natural online conference

3) Teenager agenda should follow daily routine. Proper time of the rest, good nutrition, and workout should pay special attention. Depression is never forgotten that is psychophysical processes, in such a case the physical position of a teenager needs to be constantly paid attention.

Less than 7-8 hours of sleep a day, eating without proper nutrition anemia, goitre, diseases like worm on child directly negative effect to the child`s behavior.

Mental strain in children could be solved by as asking "feeling good?", "What bother you?", "How are you doing?", "How can I help?" and this gives a positive effect. The help need to be given to collect teens` ideas by considering reasons of their depression.

In such cases, it is never proper to use words like "nothing will be happen", "all have problems", "you will live! Like others".

Because children do not want to accept the children are unwillingness, their own weakness and considering themselves as an unnecessary.

In mental depressed teenagers, their dreams and aims should be connected with expected successful future. Instead of asking questions like "Why you do not think your close people?", they should be encouraged to think about signs of beautiful, successful and bright future life.

When working with such cases, it is important to consider the reasons creating mental depression. By questions, firstly, determine the position that teens have difficulty, then helping to solve problem and giving practical help by increasing self-belief.

While working with morale reduced a teenager, it is important to identify the problem occurred and diagnosing in time by psychologists at educational places and eliminate the root of the problem. Practical help on own time shown will cause to turn to the positive changes in teens life.

References

1. Goziev E.G. General psychology.-T.: "University", 2006.
2. Bronnikova S. Lovushki odinochetvo, consilium provisorum, №2, 2007
3. Anvarovna, A. S. , & Kahharova. (2024). SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ADJUSTMENT OF FIRST YEAR UNIVERSITY STUDENTS. *JOURNAL OF EDUCATION, ETHICS AND VALUE*, 3(1), 230–234. Retrieved from <http://jeev.innovascience.uz/index.php/jeev/article/view/439>
4. Anvarovna, A. S. (2023). Constructions (models) of social intelligence in future English language teachers. *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence*, 2(4), 169-172.
5. Ataxo`jayeva, S. A. (2020). INGLIZ TILINI O`RGATISHDA LOYIXA ISHINI TASHKIL QILISHNING AFZALLIKLARI. *Science and Education*, 1(1), 403-406.
6. Umirovich, A. O., & Anvarovna, A. S. (2023). Views of thinkers on issues of family and family relations. *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence*, 2(5), 508-511.
7. Nortoji Jumayevich Eshnaye, & Shahlo Anvarovna Atakhujaeva (2021). SELF-DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AND ITS ESSENCE. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2 (CSPI conference 1), 371-375.
8. Ataxo`jayeva, S. (2023). EMPIRICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE STUDY ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS. *GULDU AXBOROTNOMASI.–2023*.

Medicine and natural online conference

9. Atakhujaeva, S. (2023). CONSTRUCTIONS (MODELS) OF SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS. *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence*

ЎСМИРЛАРДА ЎЗИНИ-ЎЗИ БАҲОЛАШНИНГ ПАСТЛИГИ ЁЛҒИЗЛИК ҲИССИНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИГА ТАЪСИР ҚИЛУВЧИ ОМИЛ СИФАТИДА

Дарвишхожаев Хасан Абдулҳакимович

University of Business and Science

“Педагогика ва психология” кафедраси ўқитувчиси

Аннотация. Мақолада ўсмирлик даврида ёлғизлик ҳиссининг шаклланиши, ўсмирларда ўз-ўзига баҳо беришнинг ёлғизлик ҳисси шаклланишига таъсири, руҳий тушкунликка тушган ўсмирлар билан ишлашнинг психологик жиҳатлари ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: ёлғизлик муаммоси, шахс ижтимоийлашуви, руҳий тушкунлик.

Ёлғизликнинг салбий (негатив) табиати – у ўзига барча психик жараёнларни бўйсундиради, шахснинг ички яхлитлигини бузади, психологик ҳимоя механизми сифатида намоён бўлади. Атрофдагилардан кўп нарсани кутишга, шахс сифатида шаклланишидаги бошқаларнинг ролини ошириб баҳолашига олиб келади. Ёлғизликнинг негатив ва позитив жиҳатлари ўртасидаги диалектик муносабатни эътиборга олган ҳолда таъкидлаш жоизки, муайян шароитларда (ёлғизликни англаганда, унга муносабатнинг фаол услуби шаклланганда, қийинчиликлар билан курашиш тажрибаси таркиб топганда, ёлғизлик мотивацияланганда) негатив ёлғизлик позитив аҳамият касб этиши ҳам мумкин.

Ёлғизлик муаммосини ўрганилганда ёлғизликнинг сурункали, вазиятли ва тез ўтиб кетувчи турларини фарқлаш мумкин. Сурункали ёлғизлик ўсмирнинг ўзи учун муайян аҳамиятга эга бўлган кишилар билан узоқ муддат давомида қониқарли даражадаги шахслараро муносабатларни ўрната олмаслигида намоён бўлади. Вазиятли ёлғизлик одатда ўсмир ҳаётидаги стресс ҳолати (яқин кишининг вафоти, кимнидир йўқотиши) натижасидир. Қисқа муддатдан сўнг ўсмир йўқотганларига кўникишга мажбур бўлади. Ўтиб кетувчи ёлғизлик ўсмирнинг қисқа муддатли ҳис-туйғуларида намоён бўлиб, ўзидан ҳеч қандай из қолдирмай ўтиб кетиши мумкин. Болалиқда ота-оналарининг ажралиши натижасида улардан бирини йўқотиш, ҳиссий яқин ишончли муносабатлар ва ота-она томонидан қўллаб-қувватлашнинг етарли эмаслиги улғайганда ўсмирни ёлғизликка нисбатан ўта сезгир қилиб қўяди.

Бошқа бир фаразларга кўра, ёлғизлик ҳисси ўсмирдаги уч хил “Мен”нинг (реал “Мен”, идеал “Мен”, акс эттирилган “Мен”) ўзаро мос келмаслиги билан боғлиқдир. Тадқиқотларда тасдиқланган фаразларга кўра, ёлғизликнинг пайдо бўлишида объектив сабаблардан кўра субъектив сабабларнинг таъсири салмоқлидир. Кўпчилик ўсмирлар атрофдагиларнинг унга бўлган